

Cosmic Strings II

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This piece is a limited improvisatory correspondence of the bass clarinet and live electronics with images of “Cosmic String dynamics and Evolution”. The person controlling the live electronics will start sending audio through the Max patch and sending an image from the Jitter patch into the projector simultaneously to begin the piece. The clarinet player is controlling Jitter in realtime. The images are responding to the bass clarinet player’s 4 pressure sensors (Force Sensing Resistors) installed on bass clarinet keys and to the live electronics player’s 4 bend sensors. The first time the clarinet player sees a new image, they will play the principal tone, and then play any of the 11 possible multiphonics shown. As new images appear the player can freely choose their own orderings of the principal tone and multiphonics. The bass clarinet and live electronics players see the same image and all musical expressions except written notes are decided by their controlling sensor on Jitter patch. For example, two images are changed by sending simultaneously toward A by pressure sensor and toward B by live electronics player through mixer on Jitter. Therefore, the written score is only outline and it can be changed for performance.